

Quinazolino Benzothiazine Derivatives.* Part II

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Anthranilic acids (III) on condensation with isatoic anhydride (II) furnish Anthraniloyl anthranilic acids (V), which on reaction with carbon disulphide/sodium hydroxide give 2-thio-3(2'-carboxy phenyl) 1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydro quinazolin-4-ones (VI). VI on treatment with (a) hot SOCl_2 , (b) HCl in boiling alcohol resulted in sulphur free compound (VII) and ester (VIII) respectively. Finally cyclisation of VI to 5H, 12H-Quinazoline (2, 3-b) (1, 3) benzo (d) thiazin-5, 12-diones (I), was achieved by treating it with SOCl_2 in cold.

IN course of our studies on thiazino-quinazoline and quinazolino-benzothiazine derivatives¹, it appeared to us of considerable interest to investigate further the interaction of isatoic anhydride with substituted anilines. In the present communication, the synthesis of I is reported by utilising various o-amino benzoic acids.

To avoid the formation of dianthranilides, condensations of various anthranilic acids (III) with isatoic anhydride (II) were carried out at low temperature in the presence of sodium hydroxide². The sodium salts (IV) thus obtained were soluble in hot water

and on acidification with aqueous acetic acid furnished the free acids (V) (Table 1). V was treated with carbondisulphide and sodium hydroxide in boiling ethanol to obtain VI (Table 2). Its IR absorption spectrum exhibited two sharp bands at 1685 and 1660 cm^{-1} (for two carbonyl functions). O-H and N-H stretchings appeared at 3240 and 3190 cm^{-1} .

The mass spectrum of VI (R = H) (Chart 1) showed the molecular ion (M^+) peak (also the base peak) at (a) m/e 298. Here, the structural assignments to some of the major fragments in the break-down of VI (R = H) have been suggested. A strong peak at

TABLE 1. ANTHRANILOYL ANTHRANILIC ACIDS (V)

Sl.No.	Anthranilic acid used	Product formed	Yield (%)**	m.p. °C	mol. formula	N (%)	
						Found	Regd.
1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.
1.	Unsubstituted	H	83	202	known		
2.	5-Methyl-	CH_3^*	80	196	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$	10.16	10.37
3.	5-Chloro-	Cl	76	218	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_3$	9.93	9.65
4.	5-Bromo-	Br	74	224	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{BrN}_2\text{O}_3$	8.00	8.35

** All the compounds were crystallised from ethanol.

* Satisfactory C, H, analysis have also been obtained from the compound.

TABLE 2. 2-THIO-3-(2'-CARBOXY PHENYL)-1, 2, 3, 4-(TETRA-HYDROQUINALIN-4-ONE (VI)

Sl.No.	Product formed R	Yield (%)*	m.p. °C	Mol. formula	N (%)	
					Found	Reqd.
1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.
1.	H^{**}	80	230	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$	9.00	9.39
2.	CH_3	77	240	$\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$	8.72	8.97
3.	Cl	71	244	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{ClN}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$	8.13	8.43
4.	Br	69	248	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_9\text{BrN}_2\text{O}_3\text{S}$	7.19	7.42

* All the compounds were crystallised from ethanol.

+ Satisfactory C, H, analysis have also been obtained for the compound.

*For Part I see reference 1.

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(b) m/e 280 which corresponds to an ion, was produced probably by the loss of elements of water molecule affecting the cyclisation. On the other hand, the formation of a fragment ion (c) m/e 281 can be

explained by the expulsion of OH, which was followed by the further loss of CO molecule to form a very abundant ion (d) m/e 253. Also a peak at

radical⁷ (q) m/e 76 which loses a hydrogen radical to give the benzyne cation (r) m/e 75.

Cyclisation of VI was tried by (a) refluxing in dry ethanol, (b) treating with P₂O₅ in boiling dry benzene, but it remained unaffected in both the cases. (c) Action of SOCl₂ on VI (R = H) in refluxing benzene resulted in the loss of sulphur, identified to be VII through its m.p., m.m.p. and R_f value with the authentic sample⁶. (d) Alternatively, by the passage of hydrogen chloride through VI in boiling absolute ethanol, a product insoluble in sodium carbonate solution but soluble in 2% aqueous sodium hydroxide, was obtained. On further investigation, it was characterised to be ethyl ester* (VIII) (Table 3).

CHART I- FRAGMENTATION PATTERN OF VI (R=H)

(p) m/e 254 arisen from a fragment representing the loss of 44 mass units³ (CO₂) from the parent ion. A very abundant ion (f) m/e 264 is formed by the loss of H₂S. This lactone (f) is further decomposed by the loss of CO followed by capture of hydrogen atom to form an ion (g) m/e 237. A retro Diels-Alder decomposition⁴ is the main cleavage process of the quinazolone systems like Arborine⁵. Here, similarly, this cleavage occurs at (p)→(j)+(k); (d)→(j)+(l); (c)→(j)+(n). Ion (j) further breaks down with the loss of CO molecule to form a fragment ion, (m) m/e 91. Ion (p) under reverse RDA³ cleavage forms two radical cations (j) m/e 119 and benzyne

The cyclisation of VI to get I was finally achieved by treating it with thionyl chloride at 5°-10° or on refluxing it in dry dioxan (in the absence of protonic reagent).

Experimental

Melting points were determined by capillary method and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer 337 grating instrument and NMR spectra were run on a varian A-60 instrument using TMS as internal reference. Mass spectra were taken on CEC-21-110B double focussing mass spectrometer operating at 70 eV using a direct inlet system.

Condensation of isatoic anhydride (II) with anthranilic acids (III): Formation of anthraniloyl anthranilic acids (V). General Procedure: Equimolar quantities of II and III were mixed up in small amount of water. The reaction mixture was maintained at 50°-60° on a water bath and aqueous sodium hydroxide (1.15N) (1.5 mole for 1 mole of II) was added gradually.

There was brisk evolution of carbon dioxide and heating was continued till the completion of the reaction (evolution of carbon dioxide ceased). It was cooled and filtered. The residue, sodium salt (IV) was soluble in hot water and on acidification with aqueous acetic acid, yielded V. The filtrate on treatment with aqueous acetic acid gave crude V which on crystallisation from ethanol furnished the products (Table 1).

2-Thio-3-(2'-carboxy phenyl)1,2,3,4-tetrahydro quinazolin-4-ones (VI). *General Procedure*: Carbondisulphide (0.01 mole) was added to a cooled solution of V (0.01 mole) in ethanol (40 ml.) containing sodium hydroxide (0.02 mole), followed by gentle refluxing. After about 1 hr. a light yellow solid began to separate in increasing amount with time. Heating was stopped when evolution of H₂S ceased. It was cooled and the solid collected under suction, dissolved in H₂O, filtered and the filtrate was precipitated with aqueous acetic acid. The light yellow precipitates were collected and crystallised from ethanol (Table 2).

Attempted cyclisation of VI (R = H)

(a) VI (R = H) (1 g) was refluxed in 30 ml of dry ethanol for 10 hr. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and residue was found to be VI back.

(b) VI (R = H) (1.49 g, 0.005 mole) was refluxed in dry benzene (40 ml) containing P₂O₅ (1.50 g) for 7 hr. The reaction mixture was cooled and decomposed with H₂O. The benzene was evaporated on steam bath. The aqueous solution was basified with sodium carbonate, which on neutralization with acetic acid gave back VI (R = H) quantitatively.

(c) 2-Oxo-3-(2'-carboxy phenyl)1,2,3,4-tetrahydro quinazolin-4-one (VII)

Equimolar quantities of VI (R = H) and thionyl chloride were refluxed in dry benzene for 1 hr. After removing the solvent the residue was treated with 10% sodium carbonate solution where whole of the mass went into solution. On acidification with aqueous acetic acid followed by filtration, a sulphur free white product was obtained. It was crystallised

from dioxan-alcohol mixture, m.p. 293° and was characterized to be VII on the basis of some R_f value and no depression in m.m.p. with the authentic sample⁸.

(d) 2-Thio-3-(2'-carboxy phenyl) 1,2,3,4-tetrahydro-quinazolinones (VIII)

Dry hydrogen chloride was passed through a refluxing solution of VI (R = H), (1.49 g) in dry ethanol (30 ml) for 3 hr when a white solid was separated out. The solvent was distilled off and the residue was treated with 10% aqueous sodium carbonate to remove the unreacted free acid compound and filtered. The filtrate on acidification with aqueous acetic acid gave back VI (R = H), m.p. and m.m.p. 230°. The precipitates (VIII) was crystallised from benzene to afford silky needles of VIII, m.p. 204°, 1.97 g (78%) (Table 3).

5H, 12H-Quinazolino (2,3-b) (1,3) benzo (d) thiazin-5, 12-diones (I).

General Procedure: (a) Thionyl chloride (4 ml.) was added to VI (R = H, 1 g) in cold. There was an instantaneous evolution of HCl gas leading to the formation of a clear solution followed by a yellow solid mass within half min. After keeping it for ½ hr at room temperature, the excess of thionyl chloride was removed under vacuum using small batches of dry ether. It was treated with 10% sodium carbonate solution and filtered and well washed with water. The residue thus obtained was crystallised from glacial acetic acid to furnish light yellow crystalline product (I) m.p. 300°, 0.9 g (95.7%) (Table 4). The filtrate on treatment with aqueous acetic acid gave small amount of VI (R = H) sufficient for m.p. and m.m.p. 230°. IR of I (R = H): max. 3040, 1690, 1665, 1610, 1590, 1540, 1480, 1450, 1400, 1325, 1275, 1265 and 1235 cm⁻¹.

Mass spectrum of I (R = H). (Found: mol. ion 280; mol. wt. Calcd. for C₁₅H₈N₂O₂S was 280).

(b) VI (R = H 1 g) was refluxed in dry dioxan (30 ml) for 5 hr. After distilling of the solvent, the residue was treated as above to yield I (0.80 g).

TABLE 3. 2-THIO-3-(2-CARBETHOXYPHENYL)-1, 2, 3, 4-TETRAHYDROQUINAZOLIN-4-ONES (VIII)

Sl.No.	Product Formed	Yield (%) [*]	m.p. °C	Mol. Formula	N (%)	
					Found	Reqd.
1.	H [*]	78	204	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	8.23	8.58
2.	CH ₃	76	213	C ₁₈ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂ S	7.91	8.23
3.	Cl	72	185	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	7.52	7.77
4.	Br	68.5	169	C ₁₇ H ₁₃ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	6.50	6.91

^{*} Compound Nos. 2, 3 and 4 have been crystallised from ethanol and No. 1 from benzene.

[†] Satisfactory C, H analysis have also been obtained for the compound.

TABLE 4. 5H, 12H-QUINAZOLINO (2, 3-b) (1, 3) BENZO (d) THIAZIN-5- 12-DIONES (I)

1. Sl.No.	2. Product formed R	3. Yield (%)*	4. m.p. °C	5. Mol.Formula	6. 7. N (%)	
					Found	Reqd.
1.	H**	95.7	300	C ₁₅ H ₉ N ₂ O ₂ S	10.04	10.00
2.	CH ₃	92.5	296	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	9.37	9.52
3.	Cl	89	306	C ₁₅ H ₇ ClN ₂ O ₂ S	8.63	8.91
4.	Br	86	311	C ₁₅ H ₇ BrN ₂ O ₂ S	7.48	7.79

* All the compounds were crystallised from G. Acetic acid.

** Satisfactory C, H analysis have also been obtained for the compound.

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